

Seed Finding in the Acts Software Package: Algorithms and Optimizations

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ABSTRACT

Seed finding is an important and computationally expensive problem in the reconstruction of charged particle tracks; finding solutions to this problem involves forming triplets (seeds) of discrete points at which particles were detected (space-points) in the detector volume. This combinatorial process scales cubically with the number of space-points, which in turn is expected to increase in future collision experiments as well as in upgrades to current experiments such as the HL-LHC (High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider). The Acts (A Common Tracking Software) software package provides a broad range of algorithms – including seeding – for the reconstruction of charge particle tracks in a broad range of detectors. In order to provide competitive performance – in terms of computation as well as physics – for future experiments, the Acts software provides highly optimized seed finding algorithms which can be configured for different detector geometries. In this talk, we describe the seeding algorithms in `tracc` which reduce the combinatorial explosion problem through the use of structured grids and k -dimensional search trees. We compare the performance of these algorithms in CPU- and GPU-based environments. Finally, we discuss seed filtering strategies for reducing the volume of output seeds which impacts the performance of other algorithms such as combinatorial Kalman filtering. In particular, we propose to combine a clustering algorithm – such as DBSCAN – and a neural network with Margin Ranking Loss for an efficient and performant seed selection.

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1 Introduction

With increasing number of proton-proton collisions, track reconstruction will pose a significant computational challenge within event reconstruction for future particle physics experiments. Although algorithm adjustments depend on detector geometry, current experiments employ similar strategies with shared characteristics and can benefit from the development of more efficient algorithms. The seeding algorithm is often used as a first step of the pattern recognition of charged particle trajectories. Seed parameters are then used as first estimate of track direction and momentum in local pattern recognition methods. It is a computationally expensive phase of event reconstruction and defines the number, the efficiency and the purity of the triplet candidates that will be processed for track finding. This note presents a significant effort focused on enhancing and optimizing Acts seeding algorithms to improve their CPU performance, as well as the development of strategies intended to reduce the number of output seeds and, therefore, minimize the time for the full tracking chain, while ensuring high physics performance.

A Common Tracking Software toolkit (Acts) [1] is an experiment-independent toolkit for charged particle track reconstruction designed for modern computing architectures and multi-threaded event processing. Beside truth-based seeding strategies, Acts includes a range of local methods for CPU-based seeding, such as the mid-point Seeding and the orthogonal Seeding. These algorithms are internally structured as sequences of steps: Seed Finding and Filtering, followed by Seed Confirmation. The main CPU-based seeding strategies in Acts will be described in more details in Section 2.

In addition, the Acts project is following two dedicated Research and Development (R&D) lines to explore new techniques and optimizations of the seeding algorithm: one for machine learning (ML) based seed filtering (Section 3.1), where ML techniques are used to select the seed candidates before they are reconstructed by the track finding, and one for massively parallel code execution, which mainly focuses on GPU accelerators and portability (Section 3.2).

2 Seeding Algorithms

2.1 The Mid-point Seeding

The mid-point seeding algorithm builds track seeds by combining 3-dimensional representations of detector measurements (space-points, SPs) defining a helical path in a homogeneous magnetic field. Finding multiple seeds for the same truth particle (duplicates) or seeds that do not correspond to any particle (fakes) increases the tracking time, so multiple constraints and confirmation conditions are applied to minimise the number of seed candidates while keeping a minimum of duplicate seeds to assure track reconstruction robustness against detector misalignment and defects.

This seeding algorithm is strongly inspired by algorithms used by LHC experiments (namely ATLAS [2]). This means that the configuration parameters are very much suitable for these types of geometries assuming a reference frame that is based on a right-handed Cartesian coordinate system whose origin is positioned in the interaction point (IP). The positive z -axis points along the beam direction, while in the transverse plane, cylindrical coordinates r and ϕ are used. The transverse momentum, p_T , is the momentum in the transverse plane and the pseudorapidity is defined as $\eta = -\ln(\tan(\theta/2))$, where θ is the polar angle measured from the beam direction.

To assure fast retrieval of the measurements, SPs are organised in (ϕ, z) bins within a fully customisable grid that covers the entire detector acceptance. The SP search is performed for each bin: the central SP is taken from the (ϕ, z) regions, then the other SPs are searched on neighbouring bins on inner and outer transverse-layers of the detector. The specific (ϕ, z) neighbouring bins used in the search can be configured based on geometrical assumptions relative to the IP to minimise combinatorics and improve the execution time.

The search starts by considering doublets of SPs (inner-middle and middle-outer). The potential middle, outer, and inner SP candidates are selected based on geometric requirements determined by the detector arrangement. This involves checking if the position of the SPs are inside the (ϕ, r, z) region of interest, for example we do not need to consider middle SPs in the outermost and innermost layers of the detector. The

r and z -distance between the doublet components are also taken into account. In addition, the propagation of the doublet to the z -axis is required to be within a customisable collision region, and the forward angle (angle in r - z plane between doublet components) to lie within reasonable bounds.

The algorithm then iterates through the selected doublets and builds triplets combining inner-middle and middle-outer pairs that share the same middle SP (inner-middle-outer), checking for the compatibility of these combinations. This is done by comparing the r - z slopes of the inner-middle and middle-outer doublets requiring them to be within the maximum multiple scattering effect (produced by the minimum allowed p_T particle) and a specific uncertainty. Then, a refinement of the same cut on the slopes is applied using a scattering term scaled by the actual estimation of the seed p_T . For the remaining combinations, the estimation of the triplets' helix radius is required to be greater than the minimum allowed radius and the transverse impact parameter (d_0)* of the seed is required to be smaller than the maximum allowed. Table 1 show some of the parameters used to configure the constrains applied during the doublet and triplet finding steps.

Table 1: List of selected configurations parameters used in Acts seed finder algorithms.

rMax rMin zMin zMax phiMin phiMax	Definition of region of interest in (r,z,ϕ) for all SPs
rMinMiddle rMaxMiddle	Minimum and maximum r boundaries for middle SPs
deltaRMinTopSP deltaRMaxTopSP	Minimum and maximum radial distance between middle-outer doublet components
deltaRMinBottomSP deltaRMaxBottomSP	Minimum and maximum radial distance between inner-middle doublet components
deltaZMax	Maximum value of z -distance between SPs in doublet
cotThetaMax	Maximum allowed $\cot(\theta)$ between two SPs in doublet
collisionRegionMin collisionRegionMax	Limiting location of collision region in z -axis used to check if doublet origin is within reasonable bounds
minPt	Minimum allowed value for the transverse momentum of particles
sigmaScattering	Number of sigmas of scattering angle to be considered in the minimum p_T scattering term
radLengthPerSeed	Term that accounts for the thickness of scattering medium in radiation lengths in the Lynch & Dahl correction to the Highland equation [3, 4]
maxPtScattering	Maximum transverse momentum for scattering calculation
impactMax	Maximum value of impact parameter estimation of the seed candidate

After selecting the SP-triplets, a Seed Confirmation procedure is applied to compare seeds with similar curvature and rank them based on a configurable quality score. For prompt particles coming from the IP, the score prioritises seeds with a large number of compatible SPs (N_t) and smaller values of longitudinal (z_0) and transverse impact parameters (d_0). Seeds with the same inner-middle SP-doublet and outer SPs from different detector layers are considered compatible with the same particle track if they have a similar helix radius with the same sign (which implies the same charge). Only a certain number of high-quality seeds per middle SP are selected to improve the seed reconstruction execution time while maintaining the high quality of the final track collections. Equation 1 describes the score calculation, with $c_{1,2,3}$ being configurable coefficients for each term. Table 2 shows the configuration parameters used for seed confirmation.

$$w = c_1 \times N_t - c_2 \times d_0 - c_3 \times z_0 + \text{detector specific cuts} \quad (1)$$

*The transverse impact parameter, d_0 , is defined as the distance of closest approach in the transverse plane between the track and the z axis of the global coordinate system. While the longitudinal impact parameter, z_0 , is the z -coordinate of the point of closest approach.

Requirements on the number of compatible SPs and impact parameters can also be defined for different (r, z) regions of the detector to classify seeds as "high-quality" seeds. Seeds that are not confirmed as "high-quality" are only selected if no other "high-quality" seed has been found for that inner-middle doublet. For optimization reasons, the algorithm only calls the seed confirmation for a certain inner-middle doublet, in case a minimum number of inner-middle-outer triplets have been found.

Table 2: List of selected configurations parameters used in ACTS seed confirmation algorithms.

<code>deltaInvHelixDiameter</code>	Allowed difference in curvature between two compatible seeds
<code>deltaRMin</code>	Minimum distance between compatible outer SPs to be considered
<code>compatSeedWeight</code>	c_1 factor in Equation 1 for seed score calculation
<code>impactWeightFactor</code>	c_2 factor in Equation 1 for seed score calculation
<code>zOriginWeightFactor</code>	c_3 factor in Equation 1 for seed score calculation
<code>maxSeedsPerSpM</code>	Maximum number minus one of accepted seeds per middle SP

The mid-point seeding is used by a number of HEP experiments. It has been optimized for the ATLAS ITk detector [5–7], and integrated into the ATLAS framework for Phase-II software upgrade program [8, 9] maintaining competitive CPU performance. The algorithm has also been successfully deployed in the reconstruction chain of sPHENIX [10, 11], CEPC [12, 13] and STCF [14], and is under optimization for NA60+ [15] and others.

2.1.1 Optimizations

In order to deal with high multiplicity environments, the mid-point seeding has undergone significant algorithmic and implementation enhancements and optimizations, aimed at reducing processing time while maintaining the overall physics performance. Some of the changes include strategies to decrease the number of unnecessary computations and iterations when building seeds, such as organising objects – e.g. SPs, doublets, triplets – according to distinct criteria (such as SP radius, doublet slope, triplet helix radius) in different stages of the code (doublet finding, triplet finding, seed confirmation). This allows for the use of binary searches rather than linear searches, which significantly improves the efficiency of searching for combinations for large data-sets, leading to a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ instead of $\mathcal{O}(n)$. Moreover, the sorting is relatively affordable when compared with the alternative of iterating through all elements.

Additionally, a complete refactoring of the neighbouring SP search was provided to improve its logic and add new features. The memory usage was optimised by improving memory allocation and a significant code refactor was conducted to restructure the code, aiming at enhancing readability, maintainability, and performance without changing the functionality.

To evaluate the performance, studies have been performed in the Acts example framework using a Phase-II ATLAS-like detector geometry. $t\bar{t}$ with $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ events were generated using Pythia8 [16]. The Acts FAsT TRACKing Simulation (FATRAS) [17], was used to simulate the detector interactions of the generated particles and a smearing algorithm was used to emulate the input measurements based on the simulated hits in the Pixel detector. Note that FATRAS, at the time being, does not include simulation of hadronic activity [1]. The seed efficiency is computed on a truth particle base. For each seed, if all three hits are associated with the same truth particle, then the seed is matched with that truth particle. The seeding efficiency is computed as the ratio between the number of truth particles matched to at least one seed and the total number of truth particles. When computing this efficiency, some selection is often applied to keep only relevant truth particles, they can be different for the performance evaluation of the different algorithms, but when no extra precision is given, they will be as follows: only charged truth particles coming from the interaction points ($R < 20$ mm and $z_0 < 1$ m) with a momentum of more than 150 MeV.

Figure 1a shows a reduction of about two times in execution time per pixel seed (PPP) when comparing version 22.0.1 and 30.2.0. Figure Figure 1b shows the seeding efficiency as a function of the truth particle pseudorapidity. The results are almost identical, with differences of less than one permille point.

Figure 1: Average seeding time in arbitrary units (a) and seeding efficiency (b) comparing Acts version 22.0.1 and 30.2.0 using an ATLAS-like geometry. The average time for reconstructing triplets from hits in the pixel detector (PPP) is plotted separately for grid initialisation and seed production for pixel sub-detector.

2.2 The Orthogonal Seeding

In addition to the seeding algorithm defined in Section 2.1, Acts implements a secondary seeding algorithm known as *orthogonal seeding*. The orthogonal seeding algorithm differs from the standard mid-point seeding algorithm primarily in the choice of the accelerator data structure used to restrict the search space for candidate SPs. The mid-point seeding algorithm uses geometric bins in the (ϕ, z) plane to allow more efficient SP selection: if the middle SP for a given candidate seed lies in a given bin, then outer and inner SP candidates must lie in an adjacent bin, so only adjacent bins need to be searched. The orthogonal seeding algorithm foregoes the use of a fixed grid in favour of a k -dimensional binary search tree, often referred to as a k -d tree [18]. A k -d tree with n SPs can be constructed in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ time and permits the search for SPs in an axis-aligned orthogonal search space in $\mathcal{O}(n^{1-1/k} + m)$ time, where m is the number of matching SPs. The orthogonal seeding algorithm embeds SPs in a three-dimensional (r, ϕ, z) space, giving a search time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^{2/3} + m)$.

The performance of the orthogonal seeding algorithm – much like the mid-point seeding algorithm – relies on a reduction of the search space for SPs. Because the construction of and search through a k -d tree are both more complex than the search through the bins employed by the mid-point seeding algorithm, the orthogonal seeding algorithm must find highly restricted search spaces in order to outperform the mid-point seeding.

The orthogonal seeding algorithm is designed to facilitate the construction of seeds in arbitrary SP order, i.e. it can construct seeds using the same $\mathcal{O}(n^4)$ doublet-based strategy employed by the mid-point seeding algorithm, but it is also designed to be used for a variety of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ strategies in the future, such as the extension of doublets into triplets through the addition of an SP at either side. A similar strategy could be used to construct seeds with more than three SPs, and the k -d tree could be extended using a fourth dimension – time – to support future timing detectors.

3 Seeding Developments in Acts R&D lines

In addition to the established seeding algorithms described in Section 2, the Acts software package features research and development efforts towards novel seeding algorithms capable of tackling the higher combinatorial complexity faced in high-pile up scenarios, such as those predicted for the high-luminosity LHC and future experiments. In this section, we detail the ongoing efforts to develop seeding algorithms relying on Machine Learning (ML) and/or designed for massively parallel architectures such as general-purpose graph-

Figure 2: Distribution of the score for the good, duplicate and fake seed (a). Seeding efficiency as function of η (b).

ics processing units (GPGPUs). It is worth noting that the results presented in this section are gathered in different environments than the results in Section 2; in particular, the results in this section are gathered using the OpenDataDetector geometry [19] a realistic virtual detector similar to a future ATLAS one. As a result, the execution time numbers and configurations cannot be compared directly to the results in the previous section.

3.1 Machine-Learning-Based Seed Filtering

Due to the combinatorial nature of the pattern recognition stage, many seeds can be reconstructed for each particle. This might result in some trajectories being reconstructed multiple times in the track finding process, slowing down greatly the track reconstruction. The duplication of the seed is a consequence of the fact that it is not necessarily possible to determine in advance which seed will lead to the best trajectory. The idea behind the ML-based Seed Filtering is to train a neural network (NN) to determine which seed, among all triplet candidates originating from the same truth particle, will lead to the best trajectory without the need to perform track finding.

This ML-based seeding algorithm will first try to cluster together all seeds that appear to originate from the same particle and then select the best one within this cluster, aiming at selecting at least one cluster per original truth particle. The clustering is performed using a 4D DBScan [20], a density-based clustering technique. All the seed are represented as point in a 4D space using their value of ϕ , η , z_0 , p_T and are clustered together based on their proximity. In the second step, we will decide which seed to keep in each cluster, for this we use a six layers NN (five hidden layers with 80, 80, 100, 80 and 80 neurons each) that will compute a score for each input seed, using information such as the direction, momentum and seed quality (Equation 1), as well as the position of its 3 hits. Within each cluster, we then select the seed with the highest score and remove the others.

To train a neural network with ranking capability, a margin ranking loss function is used, which will evaluate how good the network is at separating the good seed (the one leading to the best trajectory) from the fake (hits coming from different truth particles) and duplicate (all hits coming from the same truth particle). In training, we cluster based on truth particle information and one loss function is computed for each truth particle.

$$L(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=2}^n \max(0, s(t_i) - s(t_1) + m) \quad (2)$$

The margin ranking loss L – a loss function commonly used for information retrieval and metric learning

– is shown in Equation 2 where t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n denote the seeds in a cluster, t_1 is the good seed in the cluster, s is a seed scoring function, and m is a user-defined margin between the good score and the others. In practice, we use two different values of the margin: a very large value for the fakes (0.9) and a smaller one for the duplicates (0.3). This way we can apply a cut on the score ($S > 0.1$) to remove more than 75% of the fake seeds. The effect of these two margins can be seen in the distribution of the scores Figure 2a.

Using this filtering approach, one can decrease the number of seed obtain in the default ODD configuration by a factor 10, resulting in speed up the Acts track finding by the same factor 10 while keeping similar seed efficiency as shown in Figure 2b.

3.2 GPU-Based Seeding

The usage of graphics processing units (GPUs) for general-purpose computing is a promising approach for the acceleration of a wide variety of compute workloads, including those in high-energy physics. GPUs achieve high performance principally through higher memory bandwidth compared to traditional CPU architectures and a larger number of arithmetic logic units at the expense of front-end control logic. The latter trade-off permits significantly higher theoretical floating point throughput in predictable workloads such as matrix multiplication, but makes the development of irregular applications more difficult: care must be taken to avoid divergent execution between threads in a thread group lest performance degrades significantly.

The Acts parallelization research and development project, known as TRACCC, implements both seeding algorithms described in Section 2 for GPGPU devices. These algorithms are implemented in CUDA – the primary programming platform for NVIDIA GPGPUs – and SYCL – a vendor-agnostic programming model developed by the Khronos Group.

4 Conclusion

This document is collecting the most recent developments in the seed finding algorithms, coupled with advancements in ML-based filtering and GPU-based acceleration, which are part of the ongoing effort to enhance the efficiency and performance of track reconstruction using the Acts toolkit.

The mid-point and the orthogonal seeding algorithms are described in details. Enhancements made to mid-point seeding, with a primary focus on maintaining overall physics performance, have resulted in a considerable decrease in processing time. A novel seeding strategy, called orthogonal seeding, is highlighted, incorporating a k -d tree that can be expanded to higher dimensional spaces, enhancing its discriminatory power. Furthermore, very promising R&D results are shown through the application of ML-based seed filtering, showcasing a tenfold speed up in track finding while maintaining similar efficiency.

The presented optimizations and strategies are critical steps towards meeting the computational demands of future HEP experiments, ensuring timely and accurate reconstruction of particle trajectories while accommodating the challenges posed by high pile-up scenarios.

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